

Improving aerial topdressing for hill country through differential rate application technology and modelling

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Abstract

Conventional aerial topdressing applies one application rate on a hill country farm. However, soil and plant nutrition varies significantly over a farm. Additionally, pilots and farmers are concerned with off target application into sensitive zones, such as a neighbouring farm or water way. Off target application reduces a farmer's profitability and increases their environmental impact. Ravensdown Limited is integrating differential rate application technology (DRAT) on to their aircraft to address these issues. DRAT allows for multiple application rates to be applied over a farm, using an automated hopper door, GPS and a GPS accurate prescription map to recognise where the aircraft is located and what hopper door opening is required in that area. Field trials, bench testing and ballistics modelling were used to test and improve the performance of the DRAT system. The DRAT system increased the accuracy and precision of applications. It is also capable of minimising off target application and of delivering varied application rates. Overall, the DRAT system allows a pilot to improve the application of granular fertiliser to hill country.

Background

Within New Zealand's hill country, soil fertility and pasture productivity varies significantly. Slope, aspect, soil type, erosion and plant species are some of the factors that affect pasture production and therefore stocking rate (Gillingham and During, 1973; Gillingham et al., 1998; Suckling, 1959). Hill country farms are more variable than other New Zealand farming systems. Conventional fertiliser application in hill country is to apply a single rate by aerial topdressing. Topdressing aircraft regulate the application rate using the hopper door position, which is set by the pilot using a lever. The conventional method does not account for the variability in soil and pasture nutrition, and is prone to error because it is dependent on a pilot's understanding of the farm and their ability to judge distance while travelling at over 200 km h⁻¹. This increases the likelihood of off target application and is not an efficient method of fertiliser application.

Differential rate application technology (DRAT) allows multiple application rates to be applied over a farm. Ravensdown Limited has installed DRAT systems on some of their aircraft. The DRAT system controls an automated hopper door using prescription maps and GPS (Global Positioning System). Prescription maps outline the boundaries of the application zone and indicate what position the hopper door should be when the aircraft is in a zone. Studies have shown the benefits of a differential rate application system and GPS (Gillingham et al., 1999; Grafton et al., 2012; Morton et al., 2016; Murray et al., 2005). However the performance of the aerial DRAT system has not been fully assessed before.

There are four criterions that the DRAT system was assessed for: accuracy, precision, level of off target application, and capability in varying the application rate. Spreadmark (NZFQC, 2016) dictates an application is accurate if the field application rate is within 30% of the intended rate. Precision is determined using the coefficient of variation (CV), which is the field application rate divided by the standard deviation. A low CV is desirable. Off target application is determined by whether fertiliser is found in an exclusion zone (zero application rate). Capability is whether the DRAT system can vary the application rate so that there is a difference in the application rate between two areas. It is determined using a one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test.

To improve accuracy, precision and off target application, the DRAT system can be used in conjunction with a ballistics model. Jones et al. (2008) formulated a single particle ballistics model for the coarse fertiliser fraction (> 0.5 mm). The model was validated to predict the transverse spread pattern from an application based on the aircraft design, fertiliser properties and environmental

conditions. It was validated for a Pacific Aerospace Cresco (PAC) 600 and three common New Zealand fertilisers (superphosphate, urea and di-ammonium phosphate) and a blend (70% superphosphate/30% Flexi-N).

The objective of this paper is to investigate the performance of the DRAT system and demonstrate the capability of the Jones et al. (2008) single particle ballistics model.

Methods

The four criteria for the DRAT system were tested using three performance trials and bench testing. The DRAT system was connected to an automated hydraulic cantilever hopper door on a PAC 600. The three performance trials were completed over a three year period and on three different farms (Trial 1, Trial 2 and Trial 3). Each trial was carried out under different conditions. Trial 1 (61 ha) and Trial 3 (11 ha) were completed on hill country farms where superphosphate was applied. Trial 2 (30 ha) occurred on a relatively flat coastal farm where a fertiliser blend of superphosphate, Flexi-N, Maxi Sulphur Super and trace elements was applied. Different sampling configurations were used as the objective and sampling process was refined with time. The objective of Trial 1 and 2 was to determine the accuracy, precision and capability of the DRAT system. Trial 3 looked at off target application, and capability.

Bench testing was used to isolate the mechanical/electronic/hydraulic system from the environment so that a clear understanding of the DRAT system is gained. Multiple scenarios were tested and bench testing was used to determine settings for the prescription maps, such as system delay and boundary settings. Understanding the system will further improve how it is utilised in the field.

Results and Discussion

Fertiliser particles were found to bounce out of the collectors after Trial 2. These issues were investigated and correction factors were devised for Trial 1 and 2. The collectors were improved for Trial 3 by including a bubble wrap liner on the surface of the collector. It is likely that some fertiliser particles are lost in the trials and further investigation is required. After the data was corrected, the trials had accurate field application rates. The CV achieved were lower than those reported by Grafton et al. (2012). Their study reported that pilot operated application systems could achieve a CV of 70%. The CV produced by the DRAT system are 15 – 35% lower, which is a noticeable improvement. Although the trial completed by Grafton et al. (2012) differed significantly to the performance trials undertaken in this study, no other studies are available for comparison. One way ANOVA tests of the two application zones in each farm produced highly significant results ($p < 0.001$), which means the averages of the two application zones were different and the system is capable of varying rate.

Table 1. Summary of Trial 1 and Trial 2 results

	Trial 1		Trial 2	
Intended application rate (kg/ha)	500	250	284	162
Average measured application rate (kg/ha)	402	265	241	146
Difference between intended and measured average rate (%)	-19.6	6.1	-15.0	-9.7
Standard Deviation (kg/ha)	219	134	84	78
CV (%)	54.4	50.6	34.7	53.0

Fertiliser was found in the exclusion zone in Trial 3. This was because the area was not appropriately sized and did not account for the forward motion of particles. To minimise off target application appropriately sized buffers have to be included. The size of the buffer will depend on the wind conditions, forward motion of particles and fertiliser particle characteristics. Pilots are advised to fly the perimeter of the application area first to mitigate the effects of wind and the forward motion of particles. This has the added benefit of decreasing CV at the boundaries. Ballistics modelling can help in determining the distance particles will travel forward of the aircraft so that an appropriate buffer size can be selected. The ballistics model can also be used to determine the swath width required to achieve a lower CV. This is useful when there is significant wind present during an application. A study by Macfarlane et al. (1987) found that increasing crosswind will increase the swath width. The ballistics model also indicates that high crosswinds will increase the swath width but the field application rate will decrease. Therefore, the hopper door opening and set swath width can be widened to compensate, and improve accuracy and precision of the application.

From this study, aerial topdressing was found to be a highly variable process. Most studies carrying out complex trials were last completed in the 1970 – 1980. They attempted to gain understanding of the process, but found the trials expensive and it was difficult to isolate individual factors (i.e. wind, altitude, aircraft velocity). Research turned to modelling. Several ballistic models were developed for aerial spreading but assumptions were made (i.e. repeatability of swath width, collector efficiency) and were not tested in the field. During this research, many of these assumptions were found to be false. Aerial topdressing is actually far more variable than initially thought and further work is required to understand the origins of this stochastic variability.

Conclusion

The performance trials found that the DRAT system was accurate, precise and capable of applying multiple application rates. To minimise off target application, suitable buffers should be included in the prescription map that consider wind and the forward motion of particles. Ballistics modelling can be used to determine these inputs. Overall the DRAT system was found to improve aerial topdressing in hill country. However further work is required to understanding the high level of variability in aerial topdressing in general, which was found during this study.

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